

Palynology: a tool in reconstructing vegetation and climate history

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Palynology is the study of pollen grains and spores. Pollen grains are the tiny male reproductive bodies produced by seed plants (angiosperms and gymnosperms). Spores are produced by bryophytes, pteridophytes, algae and fungi. Palynology has applications in various fields like paleoecology, paleontology, archaeology, forensics, allergy studies, melissopalynology, taxonomy, genetics, ecology, etc.

Fossil pollen analysis is used to reconstruct long run changes in vegetation and climate. It can also be used in tracing vegetation history in (a) individual species (b) communities correlation deposits and assigning tentative dates, **climate change** studies and study of past human impact on vegetation¹.

The primary function of the pollen grains is to provide the male gamete to the female counterpart, in order to facilitate fertilization and ultimately the formation of the seed. For transferring male gamete from male part to the female part different plants have adopted

different methods. One of these methods is anemophily. Anemophily or wind pollination is a form of pollination whereby pollen is distributed by wind². Anemophilous pollen grains are smaller in size, lighter in weight, non-sticky and produced in enormous numbers. In this process of distribution pollen grains are eventually deposited on the ground where, if conditions are favourable, they are incorporated and preserved into the ever growing sedimentary or plant deposits at the bottom of a pond, lake or in blanket peat. The persistence capability of the pollen is due to its outer wall which is made up of chemically inert substance called sporopollenin. Due to sporopollenin pollen is usually well preserved in soils and sediments during fossilization process.

Sediments containing fossil pollen have been taken from a continuous sequence of soil depths peat bogs, lake beds, alluvial deposits, ocean bottoms and ice cores. Lake sediments can provide continuous records of past climate variability and human activities making lakes

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excellent sensors of environmental change³.

Pollen grains of a particular family / species possess distinct shape, size and ornamentation. These characteristics can be used to identify the type of plant from which they came. Samples are taken from a continuous sequence of soil depths and pollen is extracted and identified from each level to create a pollen profile of an area over a specific time. An analysis of the pollen grains in each layer of sediment can tell us what types of plants were growing when the sediment was deposited and then inferences can then be made about the past vegetation of an area, vegetation succession and climate based on the types of plants found in each layer. Pollen is considered excellent for paleoenvironmental reconstruction for a number of reasons including the fact that pollen from lake sediments provides a record of past vegetation, and vegetation is acknowledged as an accurate indicator of past climatic environment of an area^{4,5}.

Using pollen data we can discover how landscapes change over time in terms of the plant life that grows there. We can learn much about the impact of natural and human processes, and of the changing climate upon plant life. Palynologists can identify many plants that were present in the past and archaeologists can then discover more about how humans in the past interacted with their environment. Human impact on environments such as deforestation or the extent of agriculture can be determined by counting the number of tree or cereal pollen in a sample.

Human diet can also be reconstructed from the study of the stomach contents which are often preserved from bodies retrieved from ancient sites as bogs. In the American Southwest, palynologists have successfully used human coprolites, or preserved feces, containing pollen to reconstruct a prehistoric individual's diet. Besides this residues from ancient artifacts such as stone tools and pottery are also helpful. Palynologists in Scotland have used pollen grains found in an apparently insignificant piece of broken pottery to reconstruct the long lost recipe for ancient Celtic heather ale.

Palynology also enables us to identify the ancient human behaviours. Pollen's tendency to settle on other plant materials or at other sites after the plant has been harvested helps us to reconstruct the individual utilization of plant resources. For example, fodder storage for domesticated animals can be identified from large concentrations of grass pollen found inside human constructions.

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